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PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF REAL-TIME PRECISE POINT POSITIONING IN EGYPT.

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ABSTRACT:

Recently, the International GNSS Service (IGS) has confirmed the availability of open access real-time (RT) GNSS precise orbital and clock products. Until a recent time, GNSS users were able to use the IGS orbit and clock precise corrections only for Precise Point Positioning (PPP) in post processing mode, which confining the accessibility of using PPP to be employed in wide range of real-time navigation applications. However, with the availability of real-time precise products, precise real-time navigation applications can be feasible through PPP with only one receiver reducing the cost and complexity of current navigation techniques. In Egypt, for precise real-time navigation, a real-time kinematic technique with minimum two GNSS receivers are commonly employed to reach to centimetre- level accuracy for surveying applications. However, recently, commercial organizations started to present its GNSS correction services in the Egyptian market through global GNSS virtual network in real time mode using only one user receiver. The providers of the commercial products have claimed to reach to decimetre- level accuracy (5 cm) however; the main limitation of such networks is the low resolution of the global stations used in corrections estimation in addition to the cost of the service. In contrast, the RT-IGS services are free and available online with high resolution of the IGS global stations employed in GNSS corrections estimation. As a result, in this research, we study the performance of RT-PPP comparing its accuracy with respect to the post-processing based PPP and relative positioning system.

1. INTRODUCTION

Real-time kinematic RTK positioning techniques deserved the merit of being the most domination technique for real-time application in both of precise positioning and navigation communities for a long time, exceed to three decades. As the performance of RTK is incomparable in achieving centimetre-level accuracy in precise applications and machine automation. To develop the effectiveness and the efficiency of RTK technique and increase its benefits to RTK users Many private companies have implemented permanently and continuously operating reference stations (CORS) networks. However, Construction of the infrastructure of these networks required an expensive investment which represented in satisfying several factors such as density, quality, functionality, integrity and robustness of CORs (Choy et al., 2016).

The limitations and drawbacks that expose all DGNSS techniques due to the cost and complexity of existing one or more reference GNSS receivers situated at known coordinates base stations and baseline length restrictions provide the PPP techniques the opportunity to play the role of the best alternative for carrier phase-based relative GNSS techniques. However, the significant limitation challenged PPP technique which represented in the long convergence times (20 minutes or more) required for the ambiguity float solution to converge to ensure centimetre-level positioning accuracy (Rizos et al., 2012). Without the needs of reference stations, PPP technique overcomes the baseline range limitation and depending on the precise GNSS products provided, for example, by the International GNSS Service IGS. PPP confined in post-processing missions due to the delay in the availability of satellite orbital and clock correction product. The IGS products latency

which related to its accuracy reach to 18 days for final products with 2.5 cm orbit error and less than 0.1 ns satellite clock error (Tomasz, 2015).

IGS to support its superiority in both of post and real-time processing missions launched IGS real-time service IGS RTS. on April 1, 2013, IGS has confirmed the availability of open access real-time products (Elsobeiey and Al-Harbi, 2016), which offered to the PPP users free and easily access through registration to have the advantage of obtaining corrections streams in real-time that enable RT-PPP and related application required time synchronization. RTS provide PPP users with a reliable and diverse real-time GNSS combination products for GPS and under experiment for GLONASS till now.

This paper is an endeavour to present in detail and sufficient results in both static and kinematic modes that require real-time data processing as well provide the potential accuracy comparisons could be made between real-time, post processing PPP and relative techniques (RTK) in order to focus on the performance of real-time PPP technique by using the IGS real-time service (RTS) for applications that require an accurate real-time solution. As still till now there are a limited number of papers presenting sufficient field test results and performance while practicing RT-PPP using RTS products. In the first section, a summary of the post-processing and product characteristics and availability and real-time service RTS product types and description of each combination was provided. The second section describes the mathematical models used in PPP technique and the errors that need to be applied in Post-processing PPP and RTK and considered in RT-PPP. the results of static and kinematic solution are presented in the fourth section. The last

section summarises this study and contains the conclusion of the performance of real-time PPP technique.

2. PRECISE POINT POSITIONING PRODUCT

2.1 Post Processing PPP Product

The satellite orbit and clock errors corrected in PPP technique algorithms using precise satellite orbit and clock corrections products which available as (sp3 and clk) files through the internet for post-processing applications and classified according to its availability to IGS final rapid and ultra-rapid products that provide the estimated satellite orbit and clock corrections with corresponding latency in the availability reach to (18 days, 41 hours and 9 hours respectively). Table 1 lists the availability and accuracy of IGS products according to IGS products description <http://igs.org/products>.

Product type	Accuracy		Latency
	Orbits	clock	
Ultra-rapid (predicted)	5 cm	1.5 ns SDev	Real-time
Ultra-rapid (estimated)	3 cm	50 PS SDev	3-9 hours
Rapid (estimated)	2.5 cm	25 PS SDev	17-41 hours
Final (estimated)	2.5 cm	20 PS SDev	12-18 days

Table 1. IGS precise products availability and accuracy

2.2 Real-time PPP RTS Product

Real-time service is formed through corporations with Natural Resources Canada (NRCAN), the German Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG), and the European Space Agency's Space Operations Centre in Darmstadt, Germany (ESA/ESOC). its infrastructure is based on 160 station operators, multiple data centres, and 10 analysis centres around the world. Now, the RTS streams contain not only GNSS satellite orbit and satellite clock corrections in real-time to correct the broadcast ephemeris, but also GNSS observations streams from globally distributed high- quality GNSS receivers. As well broadcast ephemeris can be obtained in real-time with a high repetition rate through two streams one of them for GPS, GLONASS and Galileo satellites are produced using BKG's NTRIP Client (BNC) software (RTCM3EPH) and the other one for GPS only (RTCM3EPH01) (Hadas and Bosy, 2015). The RTS products are broadcasted as RTCM state-space representation (SSR) correction streams over the Internet using the Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol (NTRIP).

The RTS products are referenced with respect to the International Terrestrial Reference Frame 2008 (ITRF2008) (Elsobeiey and Al-Harbi, 2016). Orbit corrections are provided as along track, cross-track and radial offsets to the Broadcast Ephemeris in an Earth-centered and Earth-fixed reference frame (Krzan and Przeszelski, 2016). Some latency accompanies real-time products due to the time spent on transmit the data, process observations, update the correction stream and, in case of the combined product and to combine solutions from each Analysis Center (AC) (Hadas and Bosy, 2015).

Type	Description	Orbit Ref. Point
IGS01, IGC01	Single-epoch combination solution All epochs are independent of each other, Because of no filters are applied.	APC (IGS01) CM (IGC01)
IGS02	This is a Kalman filter combination solution. The mean satellite position is computed from all AC	APC
IGS03	Same approach as IGS02, it also includes GLONASS corrections	APC

Table 2. RTS combinations Streams

3. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Dual-frequency receivers are used for the ionosphere-free linear combination can be formed to remove the first order ionosphere effect as differencing techniques are not used in PPP algorithms and no relative ionospheric measurement delays can be significantly mitigated (Rizos et al., 2012). Satellite orbit and clock errors in equation (1) and (2) can be removed using precise orbit and clock products. The general ionosphere-free equations for pseudorange and carrier-phase can be written as (Rabbou, 2016):

$$P_3 = \frac{f_1^2 P_1 - f_2^2 P_2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2} = \rho_s + c(dt_r - dt^s) + T + c(A\delta_{r1} - B\delta_{r2}) + c(A\delta^{s1} - B\delta^{s2}) + e \quad (1)$$

$$\Phi_3 = \frac{f_1^2 \Phi_1 - f_2^2 \Phi_2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2} = \rho_s + c(dt_r - dt^s) + T + c(A\delta_{r1} - B\delta_{r2}) + c(A\delta^{s1} - B\delta^{s2}) + (\overline{\lambda N}) + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where P_1 and P_2 are GNSS pseudorange measurements on L_1 and L_2 , respectively;
 Φ_1 and Φ_2 are the GNSS carrier phase measurements on L_1 and L_2 , respectively;
 T is the tropospheric delay component;
 d_r and d^s are frequency-dependent code hardware delay for receiver and satellite, respectively;
 δ_r and δ^s are frequency-dependent carrier phase hardware delay for receiver and satellite, respectively;
 e, ε are relevant system noise and un-modelled residual errors;
 $\overline{\lambda N}$ is the ambiguity term for phase measurements (this term is not integer).

A and B are frequency dependent factors:

$$A = \frac{f_1^2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2} \quad \text{and} \quad B = \frac{f_2^2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2};$$

There are several methods and models were applied to mitigate the effect of tropospheric delay in GNSS positioning techniques. The impact of troposphere as a non-dispersive medium cannot be overcome by the observation combination of L_1 and L_2 data (Krzan and Przeszelski, 2016), correction of tropospheric delay is included in the processing of data using real-time PPP software as the BNC program using the Saastamoinen model. BNC estimates the tropospheric delay per equation as:

$$d_{dry} = (0.0022768 \pm 5.10^{-7}) \frac{P_0}{g(\phi, H)} \quad (3)$$

$$T(z) = T_{apr}(z) + \frac{dT}{\cos(z)} \quad (4)$$

where $T_{apr}(z)$ = The a-priori tropospheric delay derived from Saastamoinen model.

Table 3. Errors needed to be applied in Post-processing PPP and RTK and considered in RT-PPP (BNC)

Correction Type	Post-processing PPP	(RT-PPP) Considered in BNC	Relative GNSS (RTK)
Satellite Specific Errors			
Precise satellite clock corrections	✓	✓	
Satellite antenna phase centre offset	✓	✓	✓
Satellite antenna phase centre variations	✓		✓
Precise satellite orbits	✓	✓	
Group delay differential	✓		
Relativity term	✓		
Satellite antenna phase wind-up error	✓		
Receiver Specific Errors			
Receiver antenna phase centre offset	✓	✓	✓
Receiver antenna phase centre variations	✓	✓	✓
Receiver antenna phase wind-up	✓		
Geophysical Models			
Solid earth tide displacements	✓		
ocean loading	✓		
Polar tides	✓		
Plate tectonic motion	✓		
Atmospheric Modelling			
Tropospheric delay	✓	✓	✓
Ionospheric delay	✓	✓	✓

Also, several corrections applied to PPP account for reaching centimetre- level accuracy such as phase wind-up corrections, satellite antenna phase centre corrections, solid earth tide corrections and ocean loading corrections which are required for enhancement PPP solutions, However, the pervious corrections could be applied as optional or not considered for relative techniques. In addition, it important to understand that some of these corrections are not included in the processing of data using real-time PPP software as the BNC program. Table 3 lists the errors which required to be corrected in the case of PPP compared to relative positioning techniques (Rizos et al., 2012) and the corrections take in the considerations or included in the processing of data using real-time BNC software.

4. FIELD SYSTEM TEST

The purpose of this paper is to analyse the performance of real-time PPP technique by using the IGS real-time service (RTS) for static and kinematic applications that require an accurate positioning. A Real vehicular test was conducted in April 2016 to evaluate the performance of the real-time kinematic PPP. The vehicular test was carried out along railway track from Bani Suif to Assuit, which represent challenging situations for satellite navigation with actual frequent partial GNSS outages of several seconds. The Leica GX1230 receiver was used to collect the data used in this work. The GNSS data was limited to the GPS and GLONASS code and phase observation was collected at a 1 Hz rate. Carrier phase-based relative GNSS positioning solution is used as a reference. To create this reference solution, other Leica GX1230 receiver was set up at nearby stations with maximum baselines 30 km for every setup with precisely known coordinates determined using static GNSS processing. In this research, three sets of kinematic GNSS data were used in the evaluation with approximate 60 km distance for each set of data. Figure 1 shows one of the Railway Trajectories extended totally to about 32 km of collected kinematic data. Each set of GNSS

Figure 1. Railway Trajectory

data includes approximate 45 mins of a static data before moving to consider the convergence time of PPP. In addition, GNSS data that was observed from five reference solutions used in the evaluation of the static performance of RT-PPP each setup spent more than 2 hours' observation interval.

5. GNSS DATA PROCESSING

The collected GNSS data was processed instantaneously in real-time (for executing RT-PPP technique) using the open source BNC software produced under General Public License (GPL) and available online at <http://igs.bkg.bund.de/ntrip/download>.

Figure 2. RT-PPP Technique Components

Streaming real-time GNSS data and corrections over the Internet has been one of the major duties of BNC as Open Source real-time software (Georg Weber, 2016). also, BNC was designed for the other purposes represented in receiving real-time GNSS data streams available through NTRIP transport protocol or directly from a GNSS receiver via TCP directly from an IP address without using NTRIP transport protocol which was implemented in this test. furthermore, generating orbit and clock corrections to Broadcast Ephemeris to support the implementation of real-time Precise Point Positioning RT-PPP techniques to determine GNSS positions in static and kinematic modes. Figure shows the RT-PPP technique components. Both IGS02 and IGS03 RTS streams which are based on Kalman filter estimation are used for orbital and clock corrections for GPS and GPS/ GLONASS combinations, respectively. The RTS corrections streams are linked directly to the BNC software and the rover GNSS receiver attached to the railway vehicular in real time mode. The undifferenced ionosphere-free linear combination of GPS and GLONASS code and phase observations is considered as the processing GNSS data. The tropospheric error is estimated as an additional unknown with a priori values derived from Saastamoinen model. Also, all sets of raw static and kinematic observation data were submitted to online post-processing PPP application for GNSS data the Canadian Spatial Reference System (CSRS-PPP).

6. RESULTS

6.1 Static RT PPP results

Figs. 3 and 4 show the real-time PPP solution errors in easting, northing and up direction for base stations FA and MA obtained by using IGS03 RTS streams based on Kalman filter estimation for orbital and clock corrections for GPS and GLONASS combinations. Solution spent near to 30 minutes as convergence time needed for the ambiguity float solution to converge to reach centimetre level positioning accuracy. Final PPP solution was received after 12 days from online submitting the observation data to CSRS-PPP post-processing service using until final IGS sp3&clk product became available. As expected, final PPP solution needed about or less than 20 minutes' convergence time less than RT PPP required. However, it can be noticed that the RT PPP solution accuracy is comparable to final PPP accuracy. fig.5 clarifies the difference between RT PPP and final PPP as well table 4 that lists root mean square error values in east, north, 2D and 3D directions for two techniques.

Figure 3. Real-time PPP solution errors in easting, northing and up direction for base station (FA)

Figure 4. Real-time PPP solution errors in easting, northing and up direction for base station (MA)

Figure 6. kinematic Real-time PPP solution errors in easting, northing, up and 2D direction for the trajectory

Table 3. Comparison between Real-time PPP and Final PPP solution

Station	Real-time PPP RMS (m)					Final PPP RMS (m)				
	East	North	Up	2D	3D	East	North	Up	2D	3D
St. (FA1)	0.08	0.09	0.30	0.12	0.32	0.05	0.03	0.12	0.05	0.13
St. (MA)	0.07	0.04	0.08	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.09
St. (FA2)	0.16	0.05	0.08	0.17	0.18	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.04

Figure 5. The difference between real-time IGS RTS PPP and post processing final PPP for base station (FA)

6.2 Kinematic RT PPP results

The results are plotted on figure 6 for one of trajectories test present the easting, northing and 2D errors calculated from the difference between IGS-RTS PPP solution and RTk solution as the RTK result considered as the reference solution in kinematic part., it shows that the solution converged after 25 minutes. The real-time processing and frequently updated of solution errors values plotted also on charts made the monitoring of solution convergence easiest and efficient to make the decision to start moving in kinematic application after reaching centimetre level positioning accuracy.

Figure 6 presents the comparison between the IGS-RTS PPP solution and ultra-rapid, final post processing PPP solution considering only the results after convergence in easting, northing and up directions. The RT PPP solution estimated with error values around 5 cm and less than 10 cm in east and north direction and near 20 cm in up direction.

6.3 Multi-Constellation RT PPP results

The real-time service pursued to support RTS product which confining to GPS and GLONASS correction with other GNSS system correction products. By using several open source tools such as BNC and with the availability of real-time Galileo orbits graciously provided by German Aerospace Center/ Munich Technical University DLR/TUM, the Centre national d'études spatiales CNES real-time analysis center now extend RTS users with State Space Representation for Galileo. Galileo real-time correction as a new product are obtainable via the CLK93 stream accompanied by 5-10 cm estimated user range error. As well, Now, CLK93 stream contains Beidou real-time corrections product, the credit of the availability of Beidou product comes back to the use of the extrapolated multi-constellation orbits recently provided by German Research Centre for Geosciences GFZ. the CNES real-time analysis center now provides State Space Representation for Beidou <https://igsceb.jpl.nasa.gov/> . table 4 lists the RTCM messages contained in CLK93 stream.

Orbits, Clocks & Code biases	interval	RTCM message
GPS	5 sec	1060, 1059
GLONASS	5 sec	1066, 1065
Galileo	5 sec	1243, 1242
Beidou	5 sec	1261

Table 4. The CLK93 stream description

Figure 7. The difference between the real-time GPS/GLONASS RT PPP solution, ultra-rapid, final post processing PPP solution and RTk solution in moving part

Figure 8. Multi-Constellation RT PPP results for GMSD IGS station

Table 5 Comparison between RT PPP RMS (cm) using GNSS Multi-Constellation systems after solution convergence

RMS in (Cm)	GPS	GPS & GLONASS	GPS, GLONASS & GALILEO	GPS, GLONASS, GALILEO & BDS
Easting	6.1	3.9	3.5	1.9
Northing	2.1	1.8	1.6	1.5
Up	4.9	4.5	2.8	3.0

To evaluate the involvement of the other GNSS real-time correction products, GNSS data from IGS station namely, GMSD was collected in February 2017 using TRIMBLE NETR9 Receiver with TRM59800.00 + SCIS antenna observed GPS, GLONASS, Galileo, Beidou and QZSS systems. figure 9 plots the number of satellites that processed in each system. The input data are GNSS code and carrier-phase measurements. The CLK93 precise orbit and clock real-time stream products are employed to account for orbital and clock errors and synchronized with IGS GNSS observation data using different GNSS systems combinations. table 8 shows the positioning errors in east, north and up direction for GPS only, (GPS&GLONASS), (GPS, GLONASS& Galileo) and (GPS, GLONASS, Galileo& BDS). As can be noticed that, the significant effect on positioning accuracy come back to the combination of GPS and GLONASS, the solution accuracy just keep enhancement after adding Galileo and Beidou with marginal effect compared with GPS and GLONASS that showed in figure 10.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the performance of real-time PPP technique in detail in both static and kinematic modes that require real-time data processing through using several types of RTS streams product such as IGS02, IGS03 and CLK93 to present the contribution of real-time products available now for GPS GLONASS, Galileo and Beidou system moreover, provided the potential accuracy comparisons could be made between real-time, post processing PPP and relative techniques (RTK).

The results estimated from RTS products showed that the RT PPP solution reach centimetre level positioning accuracy which predispose this technique for use in several areas in both of static and kinematic modes particularly in areas where there are lack of continuously operating reference stations (CORS). Steadily, the significant limitation expose the PPP represents in convergence time essential to reach this accuracy. Nevertheless, the results offered in this article indicate the great potential of RT PPP positioning technique, along with its further development. It will be possible to apply it in several applications as mobile mapping application using RTS corrections for enhanced its positioning accuracy.

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Figure 9. The GNSS satellite availability for GMSD station

Figure 10. The positioning accuracy for different GNSS combinations for station GMSD

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